

64. Agroforestry, carbon farming and sustainable use of water resources

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EURAF is an NGO, based in Montpellier and Brussels (Transparency Register ID of [913270437706-82](https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/transregister/details/913270437706-82)). It aims “to promote the adoption of agroforestry practices across Europe by supporting efforts to develop awareness, education, research, policy making and investments which foster the use of trees on farms”. It has a network of 31 affiliated entities in 23 countries.

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Summary

Policy Briefing 64-v1 explores the interaction between agroforestry and the EU’s sustainability and water policy resilience goals. It emphasizes the role of a mosaic tree-cover in sustainable water management, and the importance of agricultural trees in enhancing soil water infiltration, reducing runoff on slopes, and increasing water quantity in streams. It discusses evapotranspiration, and meso-scale recycling of evaporated water from agroforestry and forestry, and suggests that mosaic tree-cover is probably the optimum for groundwater recharge at a catchment scale. Literature on water dynamics is examined for both silvopastoral and silvoarable systems. The importance of increasing the cover of agroforestry on the EU Taxonomy Regulation, the Water Framework Directive and the new Water Resilience Strategy is stressed. A structure for a Water Resources Plan is provided for projects focusing on water resources, and criteria for demonstrating “no significant harm” is given for projects where water resources are a secondary issue.

1 Introduction

The EU Certification Framework for Carbon Removals ([2024/3012](#)) stipulates in Article 7 that for any project to be granted a carbon removal certificate it must at least “do no significant harm” in the six areas of sustainability identified in the EU Framework to facilitate Sustainable Investment, aka the EU Taxonomy Regulation ([2020/852](#)): (1) climate change mitigation; (2) climate change adaptation; (3) **sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources**; (4) transition to a circular economy; (5) pollution prevention and control; and (6) protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems.

The Taxonomy, is supported by more detailed delegated acts for Climate ([2021/2139](#)) and Environment ([2023/2486](#)). Together, these documents establish technical screening criteria to determine whether an economic activity either “contributes substantially” or “does no significant harm” to the six classifiers of sustainability.

This Briefing relates to Criteria 3: “Sustainable use and protection of water resources”, Recital 29 of the Environment Delegated Act of the EU Taxonomy regulation states:

*“The technical screening criteria for “do no significant harm” to the sustainable use and protection of water resources should be specified for all activities that may hinder such sustainable use and protection. Those criteria should aim at avoiding that economic activities are detrimental to the good status or the good ecological potential of water bodies, including **surface water and groundwater** by requiring that environmental degradation risks are identified and addressed, in accordance with a water use and protection management plan.”*

Further detail is provided in Appendix B of the Environment Delegated Act , which requires that:

“Environmental degradation risks related to water quality and water stress should be identified and addressed, ... in line with the Water Framework Directive ([2000/60/EC](#)) and in consultation with relevant stakeholders. Where an Environmental Impact Assessment already includes such a water assessment, no separate evaluation is needed, provided the identified risks are effectively addressed”.

This Briefing considers agroforestry’s impact on sustainable use and protection of water resources, and how “Do No Significant Harm (DNSH)” can be demonstrated for agroforestry carbon-farming projects. The use of fertilizers and pesticides is primarily dealt with in [Policy Briefing #65](#) on “Pollution prevention and control”.

The recently published **European Water Resilience Strategy** ([COM-2025-280](#)) reinforces the importance of restoring the natural sponge function of landscapes and replenishing groundwater reserves. It highlights the need to incentivise and support farming practices that recover, maintain, or improve soil health, such as organic farming and agroecological approaches, and to strengthen research and innovation, but surprisingly fails to explicitly mention agroforestry or trees outside forests.¹

Section 5 discusses the need for a “**Water Use and Protection Management Plan**”, if this is the main purpose of a land-use project, and discusses the “**Do No Significant Harm**” to water resources criteria, if the primary purpose of the land-use project is (for example) climate mitigation.

2 Regulation of Water Quantity: Infiltration, Evapotranspiration, Groundwater Recharge and Recycling

2.1 Enhanced soil water infiltration and retention

Agroforestry is the purposeful management of trees and shrubs on agricultural land. As Europe grapples with the dual challenges of mitigating climate change and adapting to its impacts, agroforestry systems have the potential to deliver a suite of ecosystem services, including carbon sequestration, biodiversity enhancement, and improved soil health [2]. The improved soil structure, organic matter content and ground cover associated with agroforestry will increase rainwater infiltration and reduce runoff, particularly in autumn and winter when precipitation and flows are high (Fig. 1). Agroforestry comprises a wide array of practices from silvopastoralism (trees and livestock) to silvoarable farming (trees and crops). Tree-rows in silvoarable systems can be integrated with most

¹ Although agroforestry is mentioned in the recent European Parliamentary Research Service Study on “The Future of Water Availability and Use in the EU” [1]

nature-based solutions² which are advocated in the *Strategic Dialogue on the Future of Agriculture* [3] and the *DGAGRI Vision for Agriculture and Food* [4].

Figure 1 The effect of tree strips on infiltration and erosion. [5]

Leaf litter and root turnover promote the formation of stable soil aggregates, which improve macroporosity and water infiltration while reducing surface runoff [6]. Higher organic matter also improves the soil's water-holding capacity, allowing more rainfall to be stored in the root zone for plant uptake [7].

These mechanisms are especially beneficial under adverse environmental conditions. Tree shading

lowers soil temperature and reduces evaporative losses, thereby decreasing water stress and creating more stable growing conditions. In Mediterranean systems, agroforestry has been shown to increase soil moisture by up to 4.6% and reduce soil temperature by as much as 6.6°C, indicating strong co-benefits in these demanding environments [8,9].

Meta-analyses indicate that transitioning from conventional systems to agroforestry can increase soil water retention and reduce water use [10,11], enhancing drought resilience and reducing reliance on irrigation [2,7]. Research reported by European initiatives such as Climate-ADAPT confirms that tree cover moderates microclimates, reduces soil evaporation, and improves access to deep water reserves [12–14]. Such regulation of the water cycle is increasingly critical in semi-arid regions of southern Europe, where seasonal droughts are intensifying [15].

Tree water uptake from deep soil layers can temporarily lower soil moisture at depth by late summer. While this dynamic may lead to increased competition for water and potential stress for crops during dry periods, it also creates additional storage capacity for autumn and winter rains. The improved infiltration capacity of agroforestry systems can help reduce surface runoff and enhance water availability later in the season. For example, increased soil water storage was estimated at 100 mm for a stand of 100 walnut trees of 12 years and 8 m high, and 160 mm for a stand of 125 poplars of 12m and 25m in height [16]. This dynamic does not impede winter crop establishment, which relies on surface rewetting, and it contributes to overall system productivity.

2.2 The evapotranspiration (ET) debate: a matter of scale and compensation

The impact of agroforestry on actual evapotranspiration (AET) i.e. the combined loss of water to the atmosphere from soil and vegetation evaporation and from plant transpiration is subject to debate. Several studies and reviews highlight a reduction in AET as a key water-saving mechanism. This effect is attributed to the tree canopy, which provides shade that lowers soil temperature and reduces direct evaporation from the soil surface [17]. The trees also act as windbreaks, reducing air movement across the crop surface, and creating a more humid microclimate within the system. This lowers the atmospheric demand for water and thus reduces transpiration rates from the understory crop [18]. Some research from temperate regions has documented AET reductions of 15% to 30% in agroforestry systems compared to adjacent monoculture fields, attributed to tree shading, lower soil temperatures, and reduced crop transpiration due to windbreak effects [17].

Yet, field-scale eddy covariance measurements in Germany found no statistically significant differences in annual AET between agroforestry and monocultures. This is explained by the “compensation effect”: AET reductions near tree strips are offset by increased AET in open alleys where wind speeds recover [19]. Other studies show that species such as willow and poplar have higher leaf area indices than herbaceous vegetation, and therefore intercept a greater proportion of rainfall [20,21]. The increased “roughness” of systems with trees also increases eddy effects and means that the potential evapotranspiration (PET) of forests and agroforests can exceed that of

² The exception is no-till farming: tree roots need regular ploughing, at least with a “chisel plough” or “subsoiler”, to break surface roots and to force structural tree roots to be created below the rooting layer of annual crops.

grassland by approximately 20% [22,23]. But, detailed measurement and modelling of non-stressed short-rotation poplar coppice at three sites across Europe indicated lower PET and AET than well-watered grass cover [24] .

A metastudy by Jacobs et al. [13] noted clear effects of agroforestry on air temperature (n=10), relative humidity (n=5) and evapotranspiration (n=6), but with effects varying among studies. The greatest variability was found for soil moisture, depending greatly on the nature of the tree planting (e.g. short rotation coppice vs. fruit and/or timber trees) and design of the system.

Thus, while the shade and shelter of trees reduces evaporation from the soil and surface crops, the trees themselves are accessing water from deeper layers and overall evaporation from the system may increase.

2.3 Groundwater recharge - a tradeoff between canopy evaporation and infiltration

Research from the EU's AGFORWARD project showed that groundwater recharge rates tend to be lower in agroforestry landscapes compared to conventional agriculture [25]. A study across the Mediterranean, Continental, and Atlantic biogeographical regions found average recharge rates of 36.9% of annual precipitation in agroforestry systems versus 43.6% in conventional agricultural landscapes. This apparent paradox arises because trees, particularly deep-rooted species, use more water through transpiration and intercept more rainfall, reducing the water available for deep percolation [25].

However, emerging evidence suggests that groundwater recharge can be maximized at intermediate tree densities. A study in a cultivated woodland in the dry tropics found that, below a certain density threshold, the benefits of tree cover on infiltration outweigh the water lost to transpiration, leading to greater recharge [26]. This is particularly relevant for seasonally dry ecosystems in Europe like *Dehesas* and *Montados*, where moderate tree cover may strike an optimal balance between productivity and water availability.

The extent of this effect depends on site-specific factors such as tree species and density, root depth, canopy structure, topography, and access to groundwater. Deep-rooting trees at the edges of rivers, such as phreatophytes, primarily extract water from deeper soil layers connected to the water table rather than directly from the river itself. These trees can support sustainable water management by filtering agricultural runoff, lowering stream temperatures through shading, and enhancing riparian biodiversity. In contrast, trees without a reliable resource of underground water have a more opportunistic behaviour and may be more competitive with crops [27,28].

Overall, while agroforestry "saves" water locally for plant use, dense tree cover may reduce groundwater recharge at the catchment scale, especially in water-scarce regions. However, going beyond the catchment scale, any water evaporated from a catchment will fall downwind and be recycled [29,30] . This leads to the concept of "climate-smart landscapes", rather than simply "climate smart agriculture" [31]. Forests, agroforestry and agriculture can be modelled at a landscape scale and planned and incentivised in a way which improves the regional efficiency of water use [32–34]. This is an approach which is missing from the new EU Water Resilience Strategy [35], and even from a similar strategy produced by Water Europe [36]. The Water Framework Directive already controls the use of water at a catchment scale [37]. It needs to be strengthened using catchment and cross-catchment modelling of the effect of land use, including agroforestry, on regional evaporation and precipitation.

3. Water Dynamics in Agroforestry

The hydrological effects described in Section 2 play out differently depending on the type of agroforestry system. In Europe, two dominant forms (silvopastoral and silvoarable systems) show contrasting water dynamics and policy challenges. Understanding these differences is crucial for designing and promoting agroforestry practices suited to regional contexts and land management objectives.

According to the pan-European LUCAS (Land Use/Cover Area Frame Survey) dataset, silvopastoral systems cover around 15.1 million hectares across the EU-28 [38], while silvoarable systems occupy a much smaller area of about 358,000 hectares.

The distribution of these systems is concentrated in southern Europe, with Spain alone hosting nearly one-third of the silvopastoral area. Significant shares are also found in Greece, France, Italy, and Portugal, home to iconic High

Nature and Cultural Value (HNCV) systems such as the *Dehesa* in Spain and the *Montado* in Portugal, where livestock graze under scattered oak canopies [39].

3.2 Water dynamics in silvopastoral systems

Silvopastoral systems make significant contributions to water regulation and conservation and are particularly valuable for enhancing the resilience of livestock farming. The tree component plays a critical role in moderating the pasture microclimate. Shade from tree canopies reduces thermal stress on grazing animals, lowering their water intake requirements and improving overall welfare and productivity. At the same time, shading reduces direct evaporation from the pasture soil surface, conserving soil moisture during dry periods. Planning of planting areas should use high-resolution base maps, and knowledge of terrain variability [40]

The combination of tree roots and permanent grass cover also improves soil structure, leading to increased water infiltration and reduced surface runoff and erosion, an important benefit for flood mitigation. Evidence from a long-term silvopastoral trial in Northern Ireland found that these hydrological improvements allowed for an extended grazing season, as pastures could better handle rainfall and be accessed earlier in spring and later in autumn. Together, enhanced soil moisture retention, extended grazing opportunities, and the varied habitat structures contribute to the ecological stability and resilience of silvopastoral systems [41].

3.2 Water dynamics in Silvoarable systems

Silvoarable systems have complex water dynamics, defined by both competition and complementarity between trees and crops. A potential barrier to adoption is competition for water, light, and nutrients, which varies with regional climate. In temperate northern Europe, shading is often the key concern, while in Mediterranean regions farmers highlight direct competition for soil moisture as the main constraint [42].

Despite these challenges, well-designed silvoarable systems can achieve higher overall resource-use efficiency than monocultures [43]. Land Equivalent Ratios (LERs) above 1.0 show that intercropping produces more output per unit of land. For example, a Danish study reported LERs of 1.14 to 1.34, showing that agroforestry required 14–34% less land, and by extension fewer resources such as water and nutrients, to achieve the same combined output of crops and tree products [44].

The mechanisms behind these efficiencies are well documented. Root plasticity enables trees to develop deeper, more vertical root systems when grown alongside shallow-rooted crops, reducing competition and increasing use of the full soil profile [45,46]. These belowground adaptations also improve tree stability and wind resistance [47]. Aboveground, trees modify the microclimate by reducing wind speed and evaporative demand. Windbreaks, when designed with appropriate height, porosity, and strip length (≥ 10 times tree height), can protect crops, sometimes at the cost of reduced yields in normal years but providing clear yield advantages under dry, windy conditions as a form of climate insurance [48,49].

Additional benefits include improved water infiltration, which can be up to 60% higher than in monocultures [50]. Complementary design approaches such as keyline agroforestry systems, which use topographic contouring to optimise water distribution, can further reduce runoff and increase soil moisture availability [51,52].

4. Navigating the European Water Policy Landscape

4.1 . The EU Sustainability Taxonomy - guidance for sustainable investments

The EU Taxonomy Regulation ([EU 2020/852](#)) is a central component of the European Union's sustainable finance framework [53]. Its primary purpose is to establish a common classification system that defines which economic activities are environmentally sustainable, thereby directing investment capital toward activities and projects that are essential for the transition to a low-carbon, resilient, and resource-efficient economy [54].

The framework is intended to prevent greenwashing and provide security for investors. The regulation sets out four overarching conditions that an economic activity must satisfy to be considered environmentally sustainable: it must a) make a substantial contribution to at least one of the six environmental objectives, b) do no significant harm to the others, c) comply with specific technical screening criteria (TSC), and d) meet social safeguards.

The detailed list of environmentally sustainable activities and their TSCs are defined through Delegated Acts. For the non-climate objectives, including the "**Sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources**," the TSC were established in the Environmental Delegated Act (EU) 2023/2486, which was adopted on June 27, 2023, and became applicable as of January 2024.

The use of the EU Taxonomy is not mandatory for all businesses. However, large companies that fall under the scope of the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) are legally required to report on the extent to which their economic activities are aligned with the Taxonomy.

4.2. The Water Framework Directive (WFD): The Primary Legal Anchor

The EU Sustainability Taxonomy does not operate in a vacuum; its water-related criteria build on existing EU water legislation. The Water Framework Directive (WFD) ([2000/60/EC](#)) [55] is the primary law for water protection in Europe³. Its core objective is to protect, restore, and prevent the deterioration of all water bodies, including rivers, lakes, transitional waters, coastal waters, as well as groundwater bodies, with the ultimate goal of achieving "good chemical and ecological status" by 2015, with possible extensions for MS till 2027.⁴

The vast majority of Europe's waterways are failing to meet this goal. According to the EEA [56] only 37% of river basins had high ecological status and 29% had good chemical status. Riparian agroforestry is a greatly underused option for river management authorities to help meet these goals.

The WFD has an integrated, ecosystem-based approach to water management, which is centered on river basin districts⁵. Under this approach, Member States are required to develop and implement River Basin Management Plans (RBMPs) and Programmes of Measures (PoMs) every six years to achieve the directive's objectives [55]. The WFD is supported by two main "daughter directives": the Groundwater Directive (provides specific requirements for assessing and protecting groundwater quality) and the Environmental Quality Standards Directive (setting quality standards for priority substances and pollutants in surface waters).

According to the Environment Delegated Act, the Technical Screening Criteria for a company (and by extension a carbon farming project) must "*reflect the need to achieve good status for all water bodies*". The EU Taxonomy therefore provides criteria for **water management plans and reporting**, while the Water Framework Directive provides the specific goals and legal requirements for water quality and quantity (Table 1)

Table 1 Relationship between the key EU legislation covering water quality and quantity

Regulation	Core Objective	Scope	Key Tool/Mechanism	Linkage to Other Legislation
EU Taxonomy Regulation	Redirecting capital to green activities and preventing greenwashing.	Large companies and financial market participants.	Technical Screening Criteria (TSC), DNSH criteria, CSRD reporting.	TSC for water objective must be designed to reflect and contribute to WFD/GWD goals.
Water Framework Directive (WFD)	Achieving "good status" for all water bodies by 2027.	All inland, transitional, coastal, and groundwater bodies.	River Basin Management Plans (RBMPs), Programmes of Measures (PoMs), monitoring.	Provides the foundational legal and scientific basis for the Taxonomy's water objective.
Groundwater Directive (GWD)	Protecting groundwater from pollution and over-exploitation.	All groundwater bodies.	EU-wide and national threshold values for pollutants, trend reversal.	A "daughter directive" that provides detailed procedures for meeting the WFD's groundwater quality objectives, which the EU Taxonomy must reference.

³ The issue of water quantity ultimately falls within the national remit of Member States and is not specifically included in the WFD. Although measured for groundwater bodies.

⁴ Ecological status assesses the composition and abundance of various aquatic life forms (macrophytes and alga, invertebrates, fish fauna), hydromorphological quality (water flow and quantify, river continuity, bed and bank structure), physico-chemical quality (temperature, oxygenation, nutrient levels, pollutants). Chemical status assesses substances like heavy metals, pesticides and persistent pollutants.

⁵ Of which there are 110 in the EU with 40 deemed to be international.

5. What should be in a Water Management Plan under the EU Taxonomy?

5.1. The Four Overarching Conditions for Taxonomy Alignment

For any economic activity (including carbon farming projects) to be classified as environmentally sustainable under the EU Taxonomy, it must meet the four overarching conditions outlined in Section 4.1. Among these, the DNSH criterion is particularly crucial for land-use operators, as it applies regardless of their primary environmental objective.

For a land-use activity to be considered Taxonomy-aligned, whether it is making a substantial contribution to climate change mitigation or to water protection, it must demonstrate that it does not significantly harm water resources. For example, a forestry operation will have a main objective of carbon sequestration activities, but it can only be considered aligned to the Taxonomy if it can also prove that it does no significant harm to water and marine resources. This makes a robust water management plan a likely requirement for any land-use project.

A revised Delegated Act is under discussion in the EU Parliament. The proposed changes aim to simplify compliance and include:

- Reduced *materiality thresholds* for both financial and non-financial companies.
- Streamlined reporting templates, with fewer mandatory data points.
- Simplified DNSH criteria, particularly for pollution prevention and chemical use, now with a stronger focus on *substances of very high concern*.
- Optional deferral for financial companies, allowing them to delay reporting detailed Taxonomy Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) until December 31, 2027.

These adjustments are designed to make the assessment process more manageable, but the core obligations for due diligence, risk assessment, and planning remain unchanged.

5.2. Meeting the requirements of the EU Taxonomy for land-management projects

While the specifics of the Technical Screening Criteria (TSC) for many land-management activities are still evolving, the EU Taxonomy's approach allows for management plans to serve as a key element of compliance.

A. Large-scale agroforestry projects with a primary aim of improving water resources

A large-scale agroforestry project, for example under the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (see [EURAF Policy Briefing #62](#)), which primarily aims to improve water resources in a catchment should develop a Water Management Plan with the following sections (Table 2).

- **Site and Catchment Mapping:** The plan must begin by mapping the physical scope of the site, including all water-related infrastructure, owned or managed sources, and the regulatory landscape. This mapping should align with the WFD's river basin and river basin district approach by considering all relevant inland, transitional, and coastal waters, as well as groundwater bodies within the district [55].
- **Water Balance Analysis:** The plan should include a quantified water balance analysis that considers inflows, outflows, losses, and changes in storage.
- **Risk and Pressure Assessment:** The plan must identify and assess potential threats and significant pressures to water bodies, such as diffuse pollution from pesticides or fertilizers, over-abstraction, and physical modifications to watercourses. These threats should be explicitly linked to the WFD's "good status" metrics for both chemical and ecological health.
- **Measures and Targets:** The management plan must define concrete Programmes of Measures (PoMs) to prevent deterioration and achieve "good status" for water bodies. These measures should be supported by clear, quantifiable targets. For instance, a company could set a target to reduce process water discharges by a specific percentage from a baseline year.
- **Monitoring and Data Collection:** The plan must establish robust protocols for monitoring environmental performance. This includes detailing the methods and technologies used for data collection, such as multi-sensor probes or satellite measurements, to track parameters like temperature, oxygen, and turbidity in surface waters..

- **Stakeholder Engagement:** The WFD emphasizes the importance of public involvement, and this principle extends to the Taxonomy framework. The management plan should document active engagement and consultation with local water authorities and interested parties to ensure a collaborative approach to water resource management.

Table 2 Components of Water Management Plan for agroforestry projects primarily focused on water resources management and pollution control

Component	Description/Key Content	Supporting EU Legislation/Principle
1. Site and Catchment Mapping	Map all water sources (surface, groundwater) and infrastructure. Align with the WFD's river basin district approach.	WFD River Basin Approach Case Study.
2. Water Balance Analysis	Quantify water inflows, outflows, losses, and storage. Analyze water consumption for all operational activities.	WFD Good Status (Quantitative), Case Study.
3. Risk and Pressure Assessment	Identify sources of pollution (diffuse vs. point) and over-abstraction. Assess impacts on "good status" and biodiversity.	WFD/GWD Prevention of Deterioration, CAP Conditionality.
4. Measures and Targets	Define specific actions (PoMs) and quantifiable targets (e.g., reduction in discharge intensity) to address identified risks.	WFD Programmes of Measures, Taxonomy TSC, Corporate Case Study
5. Monitoring and Data Collection	Establish clear protocols for monitoring water quality and quantity using relevant metrics.	WFD Annexes, Taxonomy DNSH criteria, Scientific Monitoring Methods
6. Stakeholder Engagement	Document consultation with local authorities, communities, and other interested parties.	WFD Public Involvement, Corporate Case Study

B. Large-scale agroforestry projects with water resources benefits as a secondary aim

A large-scale agroforestry project where protection of water resources is only a secondary aim, for example one aimed at carbon-farming certification, should demonstrate "Do No Significant Harm" to water resources. EURAF has proposed a draft structure for an agroforestry carbon-farming project simplified management plan ([EURAF Policy Briefing #28](#)) with ten sections:

1. **Parcel descriptions and planting plans** - including parcel codes from national IACS/LPIS systems or cadastres;
2. **Mapping of existing woody elements on the farm** - including isolated trees, tree-lines, hedges, copses, forest;
3. **Baseline measurements** - existing carbon-stocks in parcels, including soils and existing above-ground tree biomass;
4. **Monitoring carbon stocks and flows** - monitoring and modelling changes following the introduction of agroforestry;
5. **Monitoring co-benefits** - plans to monitor water resources, pollution, circular economy, and biodiversity/ ecosystems (beyond DNSH criteria);
6. **Environmental constraints** - designations like Natura 2000 (habitats and birds) and nitrate sensitive zones;
7. **Social constraints** - rental agreements, engagement with neighbours and other stakeholders;
8. **Risk Assessment** - including steps to prevent fires, and pests and disease outbreaks;
9. **Impact on food security** - what change is likely on agricultural production on the farm ("leakage");
10. **Monitoring compliance with "Do No Significant Harm"** (DNSH) criteria as specified in the EU Taxonomy.

Regarding **DNSH for water resources**, the DGCLIMA Draft Methodology for "Agricultural and Agroforestry on Mineral Soils ([May 2025](#)) includes the following description "*identify and address risks that could jeopardise the achievement of the water quality or quantity objectives under the Water Framework Directive (Directive 2000/60/EC), comply with requirements for water abstraction Directive (2000/60/EC), specifying conditions to*

avoid significant impact on water bodies. Riparian buffer zones, such as riparian forests, buffer strips, meadows or pastures, shall be maintained along streams in the activity area".

5.3 Linking the EU Taxonomy to other key policies

Common Agricultural Policy

The EU Taxonomy is designed to complement other EU policies, notably the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). While agriculture and forestry were initially deferred from the climate objectives, they are now covered by technical screening criteria. The CAP, especially in its 2023-27 iteration, already links payments to “*conditionality rules*” and provides incentives through “*eco-schemes*” for practices that protect natural resources, including water. These require actions such as **limiting abstraction**, **reducing diffuse pollution** from nitrates and phosphates, and **maintaining buffer strips along watercourses**.

The complementarity creates a strong synergy: the CAP sets the baseline through subsidies and compliance rules, while the Taxonomy adds a financial-market incentive. For farmers and foresters, CAP-related water practices can be used as evidence of Taxonomy alignment, reducing duplication. Building a Taxonomy water plan on existing CAP processes allows operators to show higher environmental performance, strengthen access to green finance, and gain a competitive advantage.

Disclosure under the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD)

The CSRD makes the EU Taxonomy’s classification system a mandatory reporting obligation for large companies. Firms must disclose how their activities align with the Taxonomy, including financial metrics (turnover, CapEx, OpEx) and narrative explanations of due diligence, as specified in the Disclosure Delegated Act.

This creates a feedback loop of transparency and accountability: a water management plan is not just internal but forms part of a public report to investors, institutions, and the public. Robust, auditable data and strong governance are essential, as weak implementation will lead to deficient CSRD reporting, with reputational and financial risks. While recent amendments simplify reporting, the obligation to provide data-driven evidence of alignment remains unchanged.

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